

THE ACTIVITY OF A TEACHER-PSYCHOLOGIST IN MODERN SCHOOLS

Utebayeva Aliya Tulkibayevna

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Senior Lecturer of the Department "Pedagogy" Shymkent University, Shymkent Kazakhstan,

Dzhamashova Gulnur Ablakhatovna

Master teacher of the department "Pedagogy" Shymkent University, Shymkent Kazakhstan

Annotation : *In order to work as a teacher-psychologist at school, a person with a comprehensive education must first understand the profession, have knowledge of the profession and have professional training. This is due to the fact that the pedagogue-psychologist has the ability to communicate with people, the ability to work, the culture of communication, the ability to behave and to communicate with people, the ability to organize, the ability to communicate with people. should. Adolescence is considered a difficult and testing period. Such an assessment depends, first of all, on the many qualitative changes that are taking place at this time.*

Keywords. *Affect, adolescent, school, adolescent, psychological.*

One of the pedagogical and psychological activities of the school is the formation of a favorable microclimate for the mental health of the child, ie for the spiritual, physiological development and the environment. When moving from primary school to 5th grade, the child will have crisis characteristics as he or she adapts to the skills in middle school. Difficulties in middle school

learning, changes in the psyche of the student, difficulties in mastering the emotional sphere, affect academic performance, mental health. Different teachers have different teaching methods, are accustomed to the rules of the school, parents complain about the decline in academic performance, regardless of the age of the child; The manifestation of affective behavior in the child's life, emotional reactions during communication, neurotic stress are observed. One of the objects of the study of ways out of the crisis of the child in the period of adaptation is the family. The microenvironment of the family is a key factor in the development of special, creative abilities of the child's general intelligence.

In order to work as a teacher-psychologist at school, a person with a comprehensive education must first understand the profession, have knowledge of the profession and professional training. This is due to the fact that the pedagogue-psychologist has the ability to communicate with people, the ability to work, the culture of communication, the ability to behave and communicate with people, the ability to organize, the ability to communicate with people. Adolescence is a difficult and testing period. Such an assessment depends, first of all, on the many qualitative changes that are taking place at this time. These changes are sometimes of a nature that radically alters the child's past characteristics, interests and relationships: it can occur in a relatively short period of time, often unexpectedly, and the developmental process can be abruptly intense. Second, the changes taking place in one of the two, on the one hand, are accompanied by various significant subjective difficulties in the adolescent himself, and on the other hand, are accompanied by difficulties in his upbringing. Adolescents do not tolerate the influence of adults. There are various forms of disobedience and protest (stubbornness, rudeness, naughtiness, cowardice, introversion). Socio-psychological issues affect the emergence of manifestations of developmental tests in adolescence.

Such qualities of a person are prerequisites for schooling and upbringing. In our country, school has always received a lot of attention. The purpose of the school is to teach, develop and educate children and adolescents, as well as to address various socio-psychological issues.

It aims to form a socially active person who will bring spiritual wealth, moral purity and physical health. However, in addition to the crises of adolescence, schoolchildren face social and psychological problems.

First of all, given that eleven years of schooling is a period of growth and development of a child who is sensitive to both positive and negative influences, at school the child faces two types of crisis: one - 6-7 years, and the other - adolescence. Adolescent students need special protection. Because, as the German psychiatrist Hutter puts it, "normal abnormalities" are more common during adolescence. However, everything is normal, it's abnormal. "There are some reasons for this change in behavior. Shendler: The purpose of the school here is not only prevention, diagnosis, but also the effective solution of these problems of students (School and psychological health of participants. The main content of the life of a teenager at school is reading, ie a lot of mental pressure. Vygotsky wrote that "scientific knowledge" is not received, memorized or taken into account by the child, it is formed and formed only as a result of great effort in all the activities of his own thinking. This pressure is not easy for all children. As a result, it is impossible to master the pressure of learning. This factor is due to the complexity or volume of the learning material, the peculiarities of the intellectual properties of adolescents (along with the structure of the adolescent student, which prevents them from fulfilling the program requirements).

The analysis of the volume and complexity of the educational material is part of the pedagogical competence. However, psychiatrists and psychologists point out that if the requirements for the child do not meet his abilities, school classes can cause neurosis.

Scientific and technological progress, the age of informatization leads to the complexity of school assessment, the intensity of the pedagogical process. Yu.A. Alexandrov, M.M. Hananashvili psychiatrists say that the condition for the emergence of borderline forms of neuropsychiatric disorders is the inconsistency of the child's social and biological capabilities in the processing of information, the speed and quantity of its occurrence. According to the authors, students who do well with all the efforts of homework are more prone to information pressure, irritability, sleep disorders, behavioral disorders, sudden changes in behavior, and so on returns the answer.

Thus, the difficulty in mastering the school program may lie in the individual characteristics of adolescents. They are diverse: there have been times when learning has been difficult, even for mentally retarded children, unless they are mentally retarded (usually not identified in preschool and not sent to special schools). Once the school has reached the required functional maturity, that is, it reaches "school adulthood". Among them, they are able to hide their neuropsychological pressure for a long time and achieve very high results. But when you reach adolescence, you have to pay for the crisis of that age and the accompanying neurosis.

One of the problems that makes it difficult to master the curriculum is somatic weakness. Teacher VA Focusing on the intellectual development and health of students, Sukhomlinsky said that "slow thinking is the result of a general illness".

Although this is a short list of activities and tasks based on the development of students' personality in schools, it is recommended to use a typological approach in the practice of pedagogical and psychological activities in schools, as it describes the tasks, difficulties, problems and methods of solving them. The typology we propose allows us to develop more generalized strategies (for each individual) of professional-pedagogical and socio-psychological work with different groups of students (typical on a certain basis).

The peculiarity of the typology of the study, which consists of psychodiagnostic and design methods (Kettel. Eisenk, etc.), the proposed diagnostics may be associated with the formation of professional training in higher education, important professional qualities, future plans based on personal needs. Typological diagnostics is based on a progressive, ie open typology method, which is supplemented by new knowledge about the person based on feedback about his ability to solve various problems of student life, his chosen strategies for resolving various contradictions, his ability to participate in student society. Typological diagnostics treats the student age as an age of reflection - not only its own qualities, but also the recognition of the qualities used in real-life professional situations. Therefore, it can be used as a

method of self-recognition, which can not be used in diagnostic methods that require more complex interpretation.

The concept of individual time management can include the results of the study of the timing of activities in different professions (for example, the French psychologist C. Godboa studied the time management of nurses working two-shift work for 20 years). There are several modes of activity that occur in different professions: the most popular is the lack of time (lack of it in the performance of the service), the limit mode (where the subject must perform the work at a certain pressure, to accelerate), the mode of expiration (creative work of writers, artists, scientists) occurs in professions), effective time regime in the implementation of work (average normative), etc. The study of how different subjects work in a particular mode of action revealed that an important factor in the organization of time is the factor of internal or external transfer of time.

The study of whether a person's time organization meets the requirements of the profession shows that different types are more effective in different time modes, and only one type (so-called optimal) is successful in all modes. Such data is also the basis for training for professional selection (for example, there are types that contradict the lack of time and, conversely, there are successful types in the lack of time). Researchers have also shown that some types do not have reflexes (images of their own actions over time), while others do not have adequate reflexes - they feel differently about their ability to act, what is really happening, and so on. This, in turn, places certain limitations on professional training at the level of consciousness and the ability to consciously regulate action. According to some other typologies, it is not possible to determine the relationship between the nature of the profession and personal responsibility (priority of the profession in terms of "share" of personal responsibility), but a number of characteristics can be developed for career guidance based on diagnosing personality type. Thus, especially in the West and the United States, the specific "factor" and image of responsibility, which has been studied in detail, is prosocial, the responsibility associated with the provision of assistance, affiliation, readiness to provide assistance. This type of responsibility is, of course, closely related to the humanistic profession (nurse, educator, etc.). Another independent factor of responsibility is related to the organization of activities, including time. We have proposed criteria for a responsible approach to the implementation of activities (quality performance of work on time, despite the difficulties and changes). It was found that some types of work were completed on time, but its level was not met at a certain high level. Not all subjects meet the requirements of self-implementation of the basic conditions of action, which are reflected in the criteria of responsible action.

Some show that they are ready for a responsible approach, but do not do it if the situation changes, the conditions of service change, if there are contradictions. This study was conducted by L.I. Dementia has found a deep connection between these criteria of responsibility and their individual nature of a certain type of superiority. The most important fact is the presence or absence of a link between motivation and responsibility. The study of motivation for high school students continued in the selection of students. In general, it was found that the level of motivation (initiative) of young people is low, which corresponds only to the personal and psychological state of people in our society who have become performers.

References:

1. Aldamuratov AA Interesting psychology. Almaty, "Kazakh University", 1991-112 p
2. General psychology V.V. Bogoslovsky, A.A. Stepanov, A.G. Kovalev, edited by. Translated from the 2nd edition into Kazakh. Almaty: 1980.
3. Лихачев Б.Т. Pedagogy Course of lectures. – М., "Prometheus", 1992 with 330.
4. Zharykbayev K.B. Psychology. For pedagogical schools. Almaty, "School", 1982.
5. Zhusupbek A. Psychology. Almaty .: 1995 -310p.

BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARINING NUTQIY KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA FOLKLOR NAMUNALARINING AHAMIYATI

Sh.U. Sariyev

Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishda folklor namunalaridan foydalanishning samarali jihatlari va usullari haqida so'z yuritilgan.

Аннотация: В данной статье говорится об эффективных аспектах и методах использования фольклорных примеров в развитии речевой компетенции учащихся.

Annotation: This article talks about the effective aspects and methods of using folklore examples in the development of the speech competence of elementary school students.

Jamiyat ijtimoiy hayotida ro'y beradigan tub o'zgarish va yangilanishlar asosini barcha zamon hamda makonda ham ta'lim tizimi belgilab bergan. Shunga ko'ra, jahonning iqtisodiy jihatdan rivojlangan davlatlarida jamiyat istiqboli bevosita ta'lim tizimiga bog'liq ekanligini inobatga olgan holda uni tobora takomillashtirib borishga e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Binobarin, Yevropa Ittifoqi (EI) hay'ati tomonidan 2000-yilda qabul qilingan "Umr bo'yi ta'lim olish masalari bo'yicha Memorandum" g'oyalari ko'ra zamonaviy ta'lim tizimi ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy o'zgarishlar asosida jamiyatda yuzaga kelayotgan yangi ehtiyojlarning faol inobatga olinishi, barcha ta'lim oluvchilar uchun teng imkoniyatlarning yaratilishini ta'minlash maqsadida barcha innovatsion yondashuvlarga nisbatan ochiq bo'lishi zarur.

Yosh avlodning ma'naviy kamolotida qadimdan nutq madaniyatiga alohida ahamiyat berib kelingan. Nutq nafaqat fikrni ifodalash, axborot almashish, til vositalaridan jarayoni yoki uning hosilasigina emas, shaxsning intellektual salohiyatini rivojlantiruvchi asos ham ekanligi psixologik va biologik nuqtayi nazardan isbotlangan. Shu sababli, yosh avlodda ilk bolalikdan nutqni rivojlantirishga alohida e'tibor beriladi.

Har bir davlatning ta'lim sohasida bolalarda nutq o'stirish tizimining asosiy tarkibiy elementi sifatida e'tirof etilgan. O'zbekistonda ham uzluksiz ta'limning dastlabki bosqichlari – maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim davrida bolalarda nutqni o'stirish pedagogik jarayonning muhim yo'nalishi etib belgilangan. Global axborotlashuv va innovatsion ta'lim muhitining shakllanishi, inson kapitalini rivojlantirishga bo'lgan ijtimoiy ehtiyojning ortishi yosh avlodni har tomonlama kamol toptirish, intellektual jihatdan rivojlantirish, bunda nutq imkoniyatlaridan foydalanishni taqozo etmoqda.

Ta'lim jarayonida boshlang'ich sinf darsliklariga kiritilib, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqini o'stirishga yordam beradigan folklor namunalari ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Boshlang'ich sinf "Ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi" darsliklarida folklor namunalaridan qo'shiq, ertak, rivoyat, masal, maqol, topishmoq, latifa kabi turli adabiy janrga mansub matnlar mavjud. Quyida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishda bir necha folklor namunalaridan foydalanish usullari bo'yicha so'z yuritmoqchimiz:

1. Ertak. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari ertaklar bilan maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidayoq yaqindan tanishadi. "Ertaklar bolalarga asar qahramonlari bilan birgalikda ham va shodlikni his ettiradigan, xasislik va subutsizlikni qoralaydigan, yaxshilikning doimo g'alaba qozonishiga bo'lgan ishonchni tarkib toptiradigan dastlabki badiiy asar namunalari. Ular bolaning axloqiy tajribalarini oshiradi".

Ertak xalq og'zaki ijodining eng keng tarqalgan namunalaridan bo'lib, unda voqea-hodisalar majoziy obrazlar orqali fantastik elementlar vositasida tasvirlanadi. Ertaklardagi qahramonlar hayoti, mardligi, topqirligi, yaxshilikning doimo g'alaba qilishi o'quvchilarni o'ziga maftun etadi. Ertakni o'rganish jarayonida quyidagi usullardan foydalanish tavsiya qilinadi:

1. Kirish suhbatlari.

2. Ertak matnidagi tushunilishi qiyin so'zlarning ma'nosini izohlash.